

Convenient Preparation of Homophthalic Acids

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Preparation of homophthalic acids by peroxide oxidation of indan-1-one-2-glyoxalates is reported. Orientation of acetylation of methyl 3,5-dimethoxyphenylacetate has been established.

INDAN-1-ones are in general converted into homophthalic acids by (i) peroxide oxidation of the related indan-1,2-diones¹⁻³; (ii) Beckmann rearrangement of 2-oximino derivatives⁴ and (iii) direct oxidation with chromic acid⁵. The synthesis of 3,5-dimethoxyhomophthalic acid, however, admitted of exploration of a more satisfactory route and it is now found that indan-1-ones may smoothly be converted into homophthalic acids by peroxide oxidation of the related 2-glyoxalates⁶ in alkaline medium. The method appears general (*vide* experimental) and 3,5-dimethoxyhomophthalic acid was isolated in 50% yield.

- (VI) R₁=R₂=CH₃, R₃=R₄=H
 (VII) R₁=H, R₂=OH, R₃=R₄=H
 (VIII) R₁=CH₃, R₂=OCH₃, R₃=R₄=H
 (IX) R₁=CH₃, R₂=OCH₃, R₃=R₄=Cl
 (X) R₁=H, R₂=OH, R₃=R₄=Cl

Experimental

All melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded in Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, model 237.

Homophthalic Acid(III): A solution of indan-1-one (1.32 g) and ethyl oxalate (2.2 g) in dry benzene (15 ml) was added dropwise over fifteen minutes to dry sodium methoxide (prepared from 0.45 g sodium) at 0° and then left overnight. The solid sodium salt, which separated, was collected and added to a solution of potassium hydroxide (5 g) in methanol (25 ml). The mixture was allowed to stand for thirty minutes and then a mixture of 30% hydrogen peroxide (10 ml) and methanol (25 ml) was added to it all at once. The mixture, after allowing it to stand for one hour, was refluxed for 2 hours. The residue, after removal of solvent, was dissolved in water (50 ml) and extracted with ether (2 × 100 ml). The aqueous layer was acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid to give homophthalic acid (0.8 g), m.p. 179-80°, mixed m.p. with authentic sample undepressed.

- (I) R₁=H, R₂=R₃=OCH₃
 (II) R₁=C₆H₅, R₂=R₃=H

- (III) R₁=R₂=R₃=H
 (IV) R₁=H, R₂=R₃=OCH₃
 (V) R₁=C₆H₅, R₂=R₃=H

Ethyl 5,7-dimethoxyindan-1-one-2-glyoxalate(I): A solution of 5,7-dimethoxyindan-1-one (0.92 g) and ethyl oxalate (1 g) in dry benzene (15 ml) was treated similarly with sodium methoxide (from 0.2 g sodium) to give solid sodium salt (0.8 g). Acidification of the sodium salt afforded the ester(I) (0.6 g)

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which was crystallised from ethanol in yellow crystals, m.p. 192-93°; IR(KBr): 1730 and 1695 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 61.4; H, 5.3; $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 61.6; H, 5.5%). It gives green colouration with ferric chloride solution.

3,5-Dimethoxyhomophthalic Acid(IV): The foregoing sodium salt (0.5 g) was added to a solution of potassium hydroxide (2 g) in methanol (15 ml) and allowed to stand for half an hour. The mixture was then treated with a mixture of 30% hydrogen peroxide (4 ml) and methanol (10 ml) as described earlier and worked up as usual to give 3,5-dimethoxyhomophthalic acid(IV), which was crystallised from benzene in colourless needles (0.3 g), m.p. 171-72° (lit.⁹, m.p. 172-73°).

Ethyl 3-phenylindan-1-one-2-glyoxalate(II): 3-Phenylindan-1-one (0.4 g), ethyl oxalate (0.45 g) and sodium methoxide (prepared from 0.1 g sodium) was treated in an analogous manner as described for (I) to give the ester (II) which crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether as colourless crystals (0.3 g), m.p. 127-28°; IR(KBr): 1735, 1690 and 1655 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 73.9; H, 5.0; $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 74.0; H, 5.2%). It gave violet colouration with ferric chloride solution.

α -Phenylhomophthalic Acid(V): The sodium salt of the foregoing compound (0.2 g) was added to a solution of potassium hydroxide (1 g) in methanol (8 ml) and allowed to stand for half an hour and then treated with a mixture of 30% hydrogen peroxide (2 ml) and methanol (5 ml) in the same way as described for the preparation of homophthalic acid. On working up in the usual manner, α -phenylhomophthalic acid(V) was obtained which crystallised from benzene in colourless needles (0.12 g), m.p. 159-60° (lit.¹⁰, m.p. 156.5-58.5°); no depression in mixed m.p. with authentic sample.

Methyl 4-acetyl-3,5-dimethoxyphenyl Acetate(VI): To the ice-cold solution of methyl 3,5-dimethoxyphenylacetate¹¹ (1.0 g) in dichloromethane (5 ml) was added acetyl chloride (3.4 ml) and then finely divided aluminium chloride (1 g) in several instalments with shaking. The mixture was then left overnight in a refrigerator. This was worked up in the usual manner to give methyl 4-acetyl-3,5-dimethoxyphenylacetate(VI) (0.8 g), b.p. 192-94/0.3 mm; IR(nujol): 1739 (ester carbonyl) and 1672 cm^{-1} (keto carbonyl); (Found: C, 61.7; H, 6.1. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 61.9; H, 6.4%).

4-Carboxy-3,5-dimethoxyphenylacetic Acid(VII): The above ketone (1.5 g) was added slowly to a stirred ice-cold solution of hypobromite prepared from bromine (2.9 g) and 10% sodium hydroxide (20 ml) and stirred at this temperature for half an

hour, then at room temperature for an hour and finally at 60° for four hours. The mixture was then cooled, saturated sodium bisulphite solution (5 ml) was added and then acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid to give the acid(VII) (0.5 g) which crystallised from benzene as crystalline solid, m.p. 176-78°. (Found: C, 54.9; H, 5.3. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 55.0; H, 5.0%). The dimethyl ester (VIII) boiled at 155-65°/5 mm. (Found: C, 58.1; H, 5.8. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 58.2; H, 6.0%).

The Ester(IX): The foregoing ester(VIII) (4 g) in dry carbon tetrachloride (250 ml) was treated with sulphuryl chloride (4.3 g) in dry carbon tetrachloride (75 ml) at 0°. A few crystals of benzoyl peroxide was added to it and the mixture kept in a refrigerator for 72 hours. After usual work up, the dichloro compound (IX) (2.5 g) was obtained which crystallised from benzene petroleum ether as colourless prisms, m.p. 141°; IR(KBr): 1735 (aliphatic ester carbonyl) and 1721 cm^{-1} (aromatic ester carbonyl). (Found: C, 46.0; H, 3.8. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_6\text{Cl}_2$ requires C, 46.3; H, 4.16%). The related dicarboxylic acid(X) crystallised from acetic acid in colourless needles, m.p. 216°; IR(KBr): 1718 cm^{-1} (carboxyl). (Found: C, 42.6; H, 3.3. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_6\text{Cl}_2$ requires C, 42.7, H, 3.2%).

Formylation of (IX): A solution of the diester (IX) (0.5 g) in dry ether was added slowly to dry sodium methoxide (prepared from 0.1 g sodium). Methyl formate (5 ml) was then added and the mixture was left overnight in refrigerator. Next day, it was refluxed for one hour. The mixture was then cooled and the aqueous layer was acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid and worked up as usual to give dimethyl 2,6-dichloro-4-carbomethoxy-3,5-dimethoxyphenyl- α -formyl acetate (0.2 g), which crystallised from acetic acid in colourless needles, m.p. 195°; IR(KBr): 1710, 1700 and 1690 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 45.8; H, 3.6. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_7\text{Cl}_2$ requires C, 46.0; H, 3.8%).

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References

- H. L. SLATES, S. WEBER and N. L. WENDLER, *Chim.*, 1967, **21**, 468.
- F. M. HAUSER and R. P. RHEF, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1977, **42**, 4155.

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3. J. MUKHERJEE, J. N. CHATTERJEA and S. C. SENGUPTA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, **13**, 859.
4. J. V. BROWN and G. KIRSCHBAUM, *Ber.*, 1913, **46**, 3045.
5. C. K. INGOLD and H. A. PIGGOTT, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **123**, 1497.
6. J. EISENBERGER, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1948, **31**, 1663.
7. D. S. JERDAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, **75**, 808.
8. J. N. CHATTERJEA and W. B. WHALLEY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 4127.
9. W. DICKMANN and W. MEISER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1908, **41**, 3253.
10. A. MARSILI, *Ann. Chim.*, 1962, **52**, 3.
11. O. C. MUSGRAVE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 1107.